

Job Satisfaction and Associated Factors among Nurses Working At King Abdullah Hospital at Bisha City in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Abdulrahman Omair Altufayl¹, Abdulmjeed Mohammad alkhathami²,
Naif khalaf Alotaibi³, Jaber Saad Altarish⁴, Abdulaziz Nasser Saeed Alshahrani⁵,
Mneef Majed Alqahtani⁶, Nasser Fadhel Almalki⁷

Director of Nursing, Psychiatry and Long Term Hospital – Bisha¹, Director of MCH², Head Nurse Islamic Jeddah port Health center³, Senior Pharmacist, Health Affairs in Asir Region⁴, Director of Nursing King Abdullah Hospital⁵, Chief of medical education⁶, Director of the Training and Scholarship Department at Health Affairs in Taif⁷

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Abstract: Job satisfaction of healthcare professionals is highly important in promoting employee interest and efficiency. promoting job satisfaction determines better employee performance and a higher level of patient satisfaction ultimately to gain competitive advantage and greater productivity of the organization. Aim of the study: assess job satisfaction and associated factors among job satisfaction and associated Factors among nurses working at King Abdullah Hospital at Bisha City in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study design. A total convenient sample of 385 of nurses working at King Abdullah Hospital. Data were collected using McCloskey/Mueller Satisfaction Scale. A binary logistic regression model was utilized to identify job satisfaction and associated factors among studied participants. Results: The overall job satisfaction among studied participants was 70.4%, Bivariable logistic regression analysis indicates that age, years of experience, nationality and marital status were significant variables for job satisfaction. Conclusions: Hospital managers need to develop and institutionalize evidence-based satisfaction strategies considering the predictors of nurses' job satisfaction.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Nurses, Associated Factors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nurses have a vital role in the healthcare system and are the largest healthcare workforce in any healthcare system and they significantly contribute to the delivery of patient care. Globally, nursing has been recognized as one of the stressful professions and highly susceptible to job dissatisfaction. (Chien & Yick, 2016). Job satisfaction refers to one's general emotional response towards his/her job resulting from their own appraisal or job experience and includes various dimensions and factors. Job satisfaction is also defined as one's tendency or positive feelings toward one's job (Khammar et al., 2017).

Job satisfaction is unambiguously a positive emotional condition or sensation resulted from a job or profession. Therefore, it affects individuals' attitudes towards their jobs (Nurjanah. Et al., 2020). Job satisfaction has always been a very important issue for organizational leaders, especially nurse managers, as job dissatisfaction usually leads to absenteeism, reduced efficiency, staff turnover, physical and mental illness, and burnout (Nantsupawat et al., 2017). The more content individuals feel, the more satisfied they are with their job. As a result, individuals exchange more positive energy with the surrounding environment and improve their communication with the people around them. All of these lead to greater satisfaction with the work environment and colleagues, and job satisfaction increases accordingly (Xinzhong. et al., 2018). Since nurses play the main and most important role in providing healthcare services, factors affecting nurses' job satisfaction directly impact

the quality of care. Therefore, nurses' job satisfaction has always been a vital issue to consider, as nurses who are satisfied with their job are usually committed to it and shoulder its responsibility (*Semachew et al., 2018*). However, job dissatisfaction or a low level of job satisfaction can lead to burnout, which will reduce the efficiency of manpower (*White et al., 2017*). Job satisfaction depends on individual characteristics such as age, work experience, marital status, and the ability to predict problems (*Abelha et al., 2018*).

Regarding the factors affecting nurses job satisfaction, a recent systematic reviews conducted globally noted that a range of factors are affecting nurses' job satisfaction, motivation and retention. The reported diverse factors include: nurses' empowerment at workplace, working conditions, living conditions, career development, pay and other financial and non-financial incentives (*Halcomb et al., 2018*). Another review concluded that enhancing nurses' job satisfaction, motivation and retention have positive impact on quality of health care services, improving nursing work environment and reduction of organizational costs related to recruitment and hiring of new nurses for replacement (*Buchan et al., 2018*). Previous studies have also shown that nurses' socio-demographic characteristics (e.g. age, sex, education, experience) and workplace characteristics are associated with health workers' job satisfaction and motivation (*Lorber & Skela, 2012*).

So the aim of the current study is to evaluate job satisfaction and its associated factors among the nurses.

Aim of the study The aim of this study is to assess job satisfaction and associated factors among job satisfaction and associated Factors among nurses working at King Abdullah hospital at Bisha city in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Research questions:

1. What is the level of job satisfaction among nurses working at King Abdullah hospital at Bisha city in Kingdom Saudi Arabia?
2. What are predictors of job satisfaction among staff nurses working at King Abdullah hospital at Bisha city in Kingdom Saudi Arabia?

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research design: Descriptive research design was utilized to in the current study.

Setting: The current study was conducted in King Abdullah hospital at Bisha city, Asser region at Kingdom Saudi Arabia.

Subjects: A convenient sample of all nurses 385 nurses, working at King Abdullah hospital at Bisha city in Kingdom Saudi Arabia.

Data collection tools: one data collection tool was used to carry out the current study namely; job satisfaction questionnaire sheet, it is consisted of two parts:

Part 1: Socio-demographic questionnaire sheet This tool was developed by the researcher to collect data about nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and includes: age, gender, educational level, years of experience ...etc.

Part 2: Job satisfaction questions: This part aimed to collect data about job satisfaction of nurses, it was measured by the McCloskey/Mueller Satisfaction Scale (MMSS) was used to measure (*Mueller & McCloskey, 1990*). The scale is made up of 31 items. Eight subscales were identified through factor analysis: Extrinsic Rewards (3 items), Scheduling (6 items), Family and Work Balance (3 items), Co-workers (2 items), Interaction Opportunities (4 items), Professional Opportunities (4 items), Praise and Recognition (4 items), and Control and Responsibility (5 items).

The total score of job satisfaction was classifying according to the following: -

≥ 60 % as satisfactory.

- Less than 60 % as Unsatisfied

Tool validity and reliability

Three hundred and twenty nurses were included in the study by Mueller and McCloskey (1990) to develop the MMSS. Test retest correlations of the scale were 0.89 and 0.64 at 6 and 12 months respectively (Mueller & McCloskey, 1990). Cronbach alphas for each of the eight subscales in the original study ranged from 0.52 to 0.84. Smaller alphas were found

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in the subscales with fewer items. Construct, content, and criterion validity were found to be acceptable by the authors (Mueller & McCloskey, 1990).

Pilot study:

Pilot study was carried out on 10% of the total study sample (39 nurses) to evaluate the applicability, efficiency, clarity of tools, assessment of feasibility of field work, beside to detect any possible obstacles that might face the researcher and interfere with data collection. No modifications were, so the nurses included in the pilot study are included in the research sample.

Field work:

Data collection of the study was started at the beginning of March 2022, and completed by the end of June 2022. The researcher attended to previous mentioned settings three days per week from 8am to 2pm for the nurses that worked in previous mentioned settings. The researcher first explained the aim of the study to nurses and reassures them that information collected was treated with confidentiality principals and will be used only for the purpose of the research. The study was carried out through an assessment job satisfaction for nurses regarding job satisfaction questionnaire sheet, the questionnaire took from 10:15 minutes.

Administrative Design:

An official letter requesting permission to conduct the study was directed to director of previous mentioned settings to obtain their approval to carry out this study. This letter included the aim the study and photocopy from data collection tools in order to get their permission and help for collection of data.

Ethical Considerations:

Prior study conduction, ethical approval was obtained from King Abdullah Hospital scientific research committee. The researcher met director of previous mentioned settings to clarify the aim of the study and take their approval. The researcher also met the staff nurses to explain the purpose of the study and obtain their approval to participate in the study. They were reassured about the anonymity and confidentiality of the collected data, which was used only for the purpose of scientific research. The subjects’ right to withdraw from the study at any time was assured.

Statistical analysis:

The collected data was revised, categorized, coded, computerized, tabulated and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Data were presented using descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentage for qualitative variables; mean and standard deviation for quantitative variable. Statistical significance was considered at (P-value)

3. RESULT

A-Demographic characteristics of the studied participants:

A total of 385 study participants were involved in this study, with mean age of 33.56±6.32, 40.3 % of them aged from 30-<40 years old, 44.2% of the participants had years of experiences from 5 to less than 10 years, 66.5% of the studied participants had a bachelor science of nursing, 77.9% of them were non Saudi and, 55.2% of the studied participants were married.

Table (1): studied participants’ demographic characteristics (n= 385).

Item	Variable	Frequency	%
Age in years	20-<30	117	30.4
	30-<40	155	40.3
	≥40	113	29.4
	Mean ±SD	33.56±6.32	
Years of experience	>5 years	58	15.1
	5-<10 years	170	44.2
	≥10	157	40.7

Gender	Male	12	3.1
	Female	373	96.9
Educational level	Secondary nursing education	65	16.9
	Bachelor of nursing	256	66.5
	Master	60	15.6
	Doctorate	4	1.0
Nationality	Saudi	85	22.1
	Non Saudi	300	77.9
Marital status	Single	116	30.1
	Married	213	55.2
	Divorced	45	11.6
	Widow	12	3.1

B-participants job satisfaction subscales:

Professional opportunities were the highest percentage of mean score among job satisfaction subscales of the studied participants by percentage of 67.16%, Extrinsic reward also was the second highest mean score among job satisfaction subscale among studied participants, with percentage of 66.32% of mean score. On the other hand, percentage of Co-workers mean score was the minimum percentage among job satisfaction subscales (42.64%).

Table (2): Studied participants job satisfaction subscales (n= 385).

Job satisfaction subscale	Minimum	Maximum	Mean ±SD	% of mean score
Extrinsic rewards	3.00	14.00	9.94±3.159	66.32
Scheduling	8.00	24.00	17.90±4.25	59.67
Family and work balance	5.00	14.00	9.18±2.61	61.21
Co-workers	2.00	7.00	4.26±1.18	42.64
Interaction opportunities	5.00	18.00	11.94±3.74	59.74
Professional opportunities	5.00	19.00	13.43±3.28	67.16
Praise and recognition	5.00	18.00	11.48±2.53	57.42
Control and responsibility	6.00	22.00	15.17±4.53	60.71
Total job satisfaction	47.00	116.00	93.34±15.69	

Figure (1): job satisfaction level among studied participants.

Figure 1: illustrates that 70.4% of the studied participants had a job satisfaction as compared with 29.6% of them were unsatisfied.

Table (3): Bivariable analyses of factors associated with job satisfaction among studied participants (n= 385).

Item	Variable	Unsatisfactory		Satisfactory		AOR	95% C.I.for AOR		P value
		No	%	No	%		Lower	Upper	
Age in years	20-<30	66	56.4%	51	43.6%				.000**
	30-<40	38	24.5%	117	75.5%	5.648	2.990	11.145	.000**
	≥40	10	8.8%	103	91.2%	13.859	6.015	31.930	.000**
Years of experience	>5 years	17	28.8%	42	71.2%				.070
	5-<10 years	53	31.4%	116	68.6%	.384	.160	.923	.034*
	≥10	44	28.0%	113	72.0%	.407	.179	.929	.032*
Gender	Male	1	7.7%	12	92.3%				
	Female	113	30.4%	259	69.6%	.150	.016	1.386	.094
Educational level	Secondary education nursing	22	34.4%	42	65.6%				.580
	Bachelor of nursing	77	30.0%	180	70.0%	1.337	.671	2.663	.410
	Master	14	23.3%	46	76.7%	1.819	.710	4.660	.213
	Doctorate	1	25.0%	3	75.0%	.618	.052	7.382	.703
Nationality	Saudi	35	40.7%	51	59.3%				
	Non Saudi	79	26.4%	220	73.6%	2.226	1.213	4.083	.010*
Marital status	Single	14	12.1%	102	87.9%				.001**
	Married	77	36.3%	135	63.7%	.272	.136	.547	.000**
	Divorced	15	33.3%	30	66.7%	.457	.177	1.181	.106
	Widow	8	66.7%	4	33.3%	.110	.024	.515	.005*

C-Factors Associated with Job Satisfaction

The Bivariable logistic regression analysis indicates that age, years of experience, nationality and marital status were significant variables for job satisfaction. Respondents aged greater than or equal to 40 years were 13.85 times more satisfied (AOR: 13.859; 95% CI: 6.015, 31.930) compared to respondents aged from 20 to less than 30 years. Participants who had greater than or equal 10 years of experience were 60% more satisfied than those who had less than 5 years of experience (AOR: .40; 95% CI: .179, .929). Non Saudi participants were 2.22 times more satisfied than Saudi participants (AOR: 2.226; 95% CI: 1.213, 4.083). Married study participants were 73.0% more satisfied than those who are single (AOR: .27; 95% CI: .136, .547) .

4. DISCUSSION

Job satisfaction is an assessment of workers' contentedness with their job, whether they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Job satisfaction measures vary in the extent to which they measure feelings about the job (affective job satisfaction), Or cognitions about the job (cognitive job satisfaction). Job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences *Judge, et al., (2020)*. The present study was conducted among nurses at King Abdullah hospital to assess their job satisfaction and associated factors, the results of the current study reported that 40.3 % of them aged from 30-<40 years old. These results agreed with *Halawani et al., (2021)*, who added that most of the participants (47.8%) aged between 31 to 40 years old, which significantly affected their job satisfaction. Almost most of the studied participants 66.7% had a bachelor science of nursing, 77.9% of them were non Saudi , 55.2% of the studied participants were married, and 96.9% of them were female . These results agreed with *Muallem & Al-Surimi (2019)*, who reported that more than half of the participants (63%) were females, and the majority of them (61.8%) were married.

As regarding job satisfaction the present study added that 70.4% of the study participants were satisfied by their job, and the percentage of mean score , the present study result added that the Professional opportunities were the highest percentage of mean score among job satisfaction subscales of the studied participants by percentage of 67.16%, Extrinsic reward also was the second highest mean score among job satisfaction subscale among studied participants, with percentage of 66.32% of mean score.

In the current study, the oldest nurses were, the higher their job satisfaction. Similar to the findings of this study, a similar findings were reported by *Parveen et al., (2015)* who reported that the Saudi health care industry's specific demographic characteristics are a predictors for their job satisfaction. On the other hand *Bahnassy et al., (2014)* conducted a study among nurses in a tertiary medical care center in Riyadh, KSA, and showed an absence of association between socio-demographic data of nurses and their job satisfaction that might return to that nurses who work in Saudi Arabia came from different nationalities, cultures, and societies. This interpreted our results, where all the participants were only from Saudi Arabia.

Strengths and limitations

The main strengths of this study are the high response rate 100.0% of all participants were responded. Also, the questionnaire used for data collection included different validated scales to measure our outcome. Additionally, the generalizability of the results may be limited since the study sample only involves nurses working at King Abdullah Hospital at Bisha City in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the current study it was concluded that The overall job satisfaction among studied participants was 70.4%, Bivariable logistic regression analysis indicates that age, years of experience, nationality and marital status were significant predictors for job satisfaction among studied nurses.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Healthcare facilities and decision-makers can use the findings of this study to explore the possible changes that can be implemented to improve working conditions for nurses and increase their satisfaction rates and retention. These changes can include improving the work environment, shorter working time, and more financial benefits.

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